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ETHICAL USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS AND IN
CONTRACTS: GOOD FAITH, RESPONSIBILITY AND WITH THE
PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA ACCORDING TO GENERAL DATA
PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR)

Abstract. Articolul își propune să analizeze unele aspecte privind implicațiile etice legate de folosirea inteligenței artificiale în contractele încheiate în mediul de afaceri, pentru negocierea, încheierea sau executarea contractelor. Folosirea inteligenței artificiale aduce în mod clar multiple avantaje însă, ținând cont de riscurile asociate cu evoluția tehnologiei, trebuie să fie respectat principiul bunei-credințe, cu luarea măsurilor necesare pentru o folosire responsabilă a inteligenței artificiale în contracte, care să se aplice în mod etic și care să țină cont de protejarea părților contractante. O altă provocare privește protejarea datelor cu caracter personal conform Regulamentului General privind Protecția Datelor [Regulamentul (UE) 2016/679 (GDPR)] deoarece folosirea inteligenței artificiale presupune acces la date și trebuie să existe măsuri care să asigure siguranța datelor părților contractante.

Abstract. The article aims to analyze some aspects regarding the ethical implications related to the use of artificial intelligence in contracts, for the negotiation, conclusion or execution of contracts. The use of artificial intelligence clearly brings multiple advantages, however, taking into account the risks associated with the evolution of technology, the principle of good faith must be respected, with the necessary measures taken for a responsible use of artificial intelligence in contracts, which must be applied ethically and which must take into account the protection of the

contracting parties. Another challenge concerns the protection of personal data according to the General Data Protection Regulation [Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)] because the use of artificial intelligence involves access to data and there must be measures to ensure the security of the contracting parties' data.

Considerations regarding the ethical implications of using artificial intelligence in contracts. The positive impact of artificial intelligence on the business environment and on business contracts cannot be disputed, and the European Union (EU) has a policy of developing and using safe and legal artificial intelligence that is trustworthy, in the interest of people and that allows the development of the EU single market, in line with EU values and safe for fundamental rights.

The framework for developing reliable artificial intelligence that is legal (ensures compliance with the law and fundamental rights and freedoms), ethical (ensures compliance with ethical values) and robust³⁰ (functions in the interest of humanity, without intentionally causing harm) is represented by the AI Law (EU Regulation on Artificial Intelligence)³¹.

The AI Law, as the first law in the world to regulate AI through EU rules and sets a global standard for AI regulation because it promotes ethical, safe and trustworthy artificial intelligence worldwide, just as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³² set a standard for the protection of personal data³³.

Ethical artificial intelligence refers to the use of AI systems in good faith, responsibly, transparently, respecting fundamental rights and in accordance with moral principles and fairness, without discrimination, without causing harm, without manipulation, with the need for human oversight of AI in order to have control over automated decisions (including profiling), and respecting the fundamental right to the protection of personal data (protected by GDPR).

Good faith, responsibility and personal data protection when using artificial intelligence in contracts. The EU Regulation on Artificial Intelligence involves identifying harmonised rules on AI, measures to support innovation and to supervise the application of AI, with the prohibition of AI practices³⁴ that may harm the rights of individuals. The EU Regulation on Artificial Intelligence highlights a risk-based approach (low or no risks, limited risks, high risks, acceptable risks) and specific requirements for high-risk AI systems.

³⁰ AI HLEG-High-level expert group on artificial intelligence of The European Commission, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, Brussels, 8 April 2019, p. 5, https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2014_2019/plmrep/COMMITTEES/JURI/DV/2019/11-06/Ethics-guidelines-AI_RO.pdf (03.05.2025);

³¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689> (03.05.2025);

³² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504> (03.05.2025);

³³ European Council, Council of the European Union, Explainers: Artificial intelligence act, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/policies/artificial-intelligence/> (03.05.2025);

³⁴ Article 1 (2) Artificial Intelligence Act;

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The 2019 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, established by the High-level expert group on artificial intelligence, indicate the ethical principles (closely linked to the respect for fundamental rights) that must be respected in the development, implementation and use of AI systems: respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explainability³⁵; increased interest is given to vulnerable or disadvantaged groups and the need to adopt appropriate and proportionate measures if AI systems pose risks to individuals or society³⁶.

For example, prohibited practices (Article 5 of the Artificial Intelligence Act): use of an AI system that uses subliminal techniques that cannot be consciously perceived by a person or intentionally manipulative or deceptive techniques, with the purpose or effect of significantly distorting the behavior of a person in order to prevent the person from making an informed decision and to cause them to make a decision that they would not have otherwise made; use of an AI system that exploits a person's vulnerabilities to distort their behavior; use of AI systems to classify individuals over a certain period of time, based on their behavior or characteristics, which leads to prejudicial treatment.

AI ethics in contracts is closely related to the principle of good faith. The principle of good faith means that any person must exercise their rights and perform their civil obligations in good faith, in accordance with public order and good morals, and good faith is presumed until proven otherwise (art. 14 New Romanian Civil Code). The parties must act in good faith both when negotiating and concluding the contract, as well as throughout its execution and cannot remove or limit this obligation (art. 1.170 New Romanian Civil Code). The principle of good faith presupposes both the fidelity of the parties in the execution of the obligations, their collaboration during the execution of the obligations and the abstention from committing any fraud in the execution of the contract that may prejudice the other party³⁷.

Good faith in contracts presupposes honesty and loyalty between the contractual partners, and this principle also applies if AI systems are used for the conclusion and execution of contracts.

AI ethics in contracts is closely linked to the principle of accountability; thus, mechanisms are needed to ensure the accountability of AI systems, with redress measures in place where appropriate, especially for vulnerable groups³⁸.

³⁵ AI HLEG, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, op. cit., p. 2;

³⁶ Ibidem;

³⁷ Dimitrie Gherasim, *Buna credință în raporturile juridice civile*, Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 1981, p. 78;

³⁸ AI HLEG, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, op. cit., p. 23-24;

AI ethics in contracts is closely linked to the protection of personal data through the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), through the principles of transparency and accountability. The GDPR has created a solid framework for digital trust.

The 2020 European Data Strategy emphasizes the importance of developing a “common European data space” to facilitate data exchange, with European citizens having control over their data and respecting the values and fundamental rights of the European Union³⁹. There must be safeguards for privacy, as a fundamental right on which AI has an impact; the quality and integrity of data must be ensured, so that it is free from errors and the system is not biased; access to data must only be authorised⁴⁰.

Conclusions on the ethics and impact of artificial intelligence on contracts

Artificial intelligence systems must be used in business and contracts with a commitment to be used in the service of humanity, for the common good, with the objective of improving human well-being and freedom⁴¹ and with appropriate risk management to reduce them, to ensure people's trust in the development of technology and to ensure the reliability of AI, through the ethical character of AI that complements the legal character of AI. AI systems must be trustworthy, those involved in the design and development of an AI system must be trustworthy and act with trust, and subsequently, contracting parties must use AI systems to conclude and execute contracts in good faith, to maintain trust between the parties and in the AI system. AI ethics, regarding compliance with ethical principles, complements legal AI, so that the benefits of AI can be valued while respecting fundamental rights.

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³⁹ Communication from The Commission to The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, *A European strategy for data*, COM/2020/66, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066> (05.05.2025);

⁴⁰ AI HLEG, *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI*, op. cit., p. 20;

⁴¹ *Idem*, p. 5.

Data Protection Regulation/ GDPR), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504> (03.05.2025);

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СТАТИСТИЧНЕ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ УПРАВЛІННЯ ЕКОНОМІКОЮ В УМОВАХ ВОЄННОГО СТАНУ

У сучасному світі ефективне управління економікою є запорукою стабільного розвитку держави, підвищення добробуту населення та конкурентоспроможності країни на світовій арені. Одним із ключових елементів такого управління є статистичне забезпечення, яке надає необхідну інформаційну базу для прийняття обґрунтованих управлінських рішень.

Статистичне забезпечення управління економікою включає збір, обробку, аналіз та інтерпретацію економічних даних та охоплює широкий спектр показників: валовий внутрішній продукт (ВВП), рівень інфляції, безробіття, промислове виробництво, зовнішньоторговельний баланс, державний борг та багато інших.

Так, за 2024 рік, світовий ВВП сягнув 105,4 трлн дол, (збільшення на 3,2% порівняно з попереднім роком). США залишаються лідером у світовій економіці, їх ВВП становить майже 26% від загального світового ВВП. В Україні у 2024 році ВВП склав близько 7658659 млн грн (17,1%) [1].

Світовий рівень інфляції в середньому становить близько 5,8 % на рік, в середньому, рівень інфляції в Україні за 2024 рік становив 12% [2].

Рівень безробіття світовий у 2024 році становить близько 5,8%. Хоча загальний залишається на цьому рівні, прогнозується зростання кількості безробітних у світі, оскільки їх кількість зростає до 211 млн. У 2024 році середній рівень безробіття в Україні становив 14,3%, що є нижчим, ніж у 2023 році (17,4%) та 2022 році (18,5%)[3].

Світовий державний борг в 2024 році досяг рекордно високого рівня, перевищивши 318 трлн дол, повідомляє Bloomberg, цитуючи Інститут